

Relative Pathogenicity of *Fusarium* wilt isolates from various guava growing districts of Tamil Nadu in Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) under *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* conditions

Dharani Selvam¹, Devrajan Kandasamy^{1*}, Swarnakumari Narayanan¹,
Angappan Kathithachalam², Subburamu Karthikeyan³

¹Department of Nematology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University,
Coimbatore - 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

²Department of Plant Pathology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University,
Coimbatore - 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

³Department of Post-Harvest Technology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University,
Coimbatore - 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

*Corresponding author: Devrajan Kandasamy

Abstract:

Several pathogens have been suspected in causing guava wilt disease, however *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* and *F. solani* are the most important pathogens to be associated with guava wilt disease (*Psidium guajava* L.). In the present investigation, the duration of symptom expression and relative pathogenic ability of ten *F. oxysporum* isolates obtained from several districts of Tamil Nadu was assessed under *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* conditions. Of these, every *F. oxysporum* isolates produced wilt symptoms either on all three replicates or on a single plant showing 80% wilt. It was noticed that different isolates caused wilting at a variable period of time indicating difference in their relative aggressiveness or virulence. Earliest symptom of wilt was recorded in isolates GF1 and GF4 of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii*. In both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* conditions, the results concluded that the isolates GF1 obtained from Malumichampatti, Coimbatore and GF4 from Seethapatti, Tiruchirapalli were found to be highly pathogenic compared to that of all other isolates. Under *in vivo* conditions, the soil inoculation strategy has been demonstrated to be relevant and dependable for guava wilt replication (80 - 85%). Thus, the varying aggressiveness or virulence of different pathogenic isolates in the soil may explain the erratic distribution and prevalence of guava wilt in various geographic regions.

Key words: Relative pathogenicity, *F. oxysporum* isolates, *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* study, Guava

Introduction

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) wilt is the most destructive disease, causing 5-60% loss in guava fruit yield in India (Misra and Shukla 2002). In Tamil Nadu, the farmers have been facing a unique problem in guava orchards where the trees show sudden yellowing followed by bronzing and marginal necrosis of the leaves, delayed and poor flowering, shedding of leaves, reductions in fruit size, and decreased guava yields leading to complete destruction of the orchards within a short span of 1–2 years of planting. (Ashokkumar and Poornima, 2019), Ashokkumar et al., 2019. Das Gupta and Rai (1947) identified *Fusarium* spp. as the cause of guava wilt, which was later verified as *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* (Prasad et al. 1952). *Fusarium* is a global soil-borne fungus that colonizes the host's vascular system and impairs the movement of water and nutrients to the plant's upper half (Gupta and Misra 2012). Although various pathogens are noticed to cause wilt in guava, among them, two species of *Fusarium* i.e. *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* (Prasad et al 1952; Anonymous 1953; Edward 1960 and Pandey and Dwivedi 1985) and *F. solani* (Chattopadhyay and Sengupta 1955; Sohi 1985; Dwivedi et al 1988) had been extensively indicated as the causal agents of the disease. Edward (1960) revealed pathogenic diversity of *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* isolates but found no association between pathogen isolated and pathogenicity. Various researchers examined different pathogenicity test methods for guava wilt (Mathur and Jain 1960; Misra and Pandey 2000a; and Dwivedi et al 1988). However, soil inoculation technique has also been used (Kala et al., 2016). Some guava plants require only two weeks time for wilting, while others take longer time (Misra and Pandey 2000b). This may be due to variable virulence of the different isolates of the pathogen. Hence, the present study was carried out under both *in-vitro* and *in-vivo* conditions to confirm the relative pathogenic capacity of 10 *F. oxysporum* isolates of guava wilt pathogens collected from the different guava growing areas in Tamil Nadu. The detection of virulent *F. oxysporum* isolate may be responsible for developing successful management strategies against reducing the severity of wilt in guava plants in developing orchards.

Materials and Methods

Progressive radial growth and sporulation of different *F. oxysporum* isolates on PDA media by agar plate assay method under *in-vitro* condition:

The virulence of the fungal isolate under laboratory condition was determined based on radial growth parameter and spore load assessment by Agar plate assay method. A fungal disc (5mm diameter) of each fungal isolate was transferred to a petridish containing 10 ml of PDA medium. The plates inoculated with the fungal disc was sealed thoroughly and incubated under room temperature ($28\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) for about 7 days. The observation on radial growth of the each fungal isolates was calculated at every 24 hrs interval for about 7 days. About 3 replications was maintained for each fungal isolate. The spore load assessment was performed using Heamocytometer.

Virulence study of different *F. oxysporum* isolates in Guava under *in-vivo* condition:

Soil inoculation technique by Sand Maize Medium

The soil inoculation technique was performed as suggested by Kala et al., (2016). The fungus *F. oxysporum* was mass multiplied in sand maize meal medium and cultured at $27\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 7 days. In a 250 ml conical flask, 90 g of riverbed sand, 10 g of maize meal, and 20 ml of distilled water were combined to make a sand maize meal medium. The flask's sterile medium was infected with a piece of actively growing fungal culture and incubated at $27\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 days. Fully grown fungal inoculum was properly mixed with sterile soil in a 1:10 ratio before being placed in pots. Before transplanting the seedlings, the soil was watered for one week.

Pot culture experiment under *in-vivo* condition:

Pathogenicity test was performed on two-month-old guava seedlings (Lucknow 49). The seedlings' roots were rinsed with tap water to remove any clinging particles adhered over the root tissues. The root's tip was cut with sterile scissors before being transplanted into 5 kg pots filled with soil mixed with fungal mycelium (5g/kg of soil). The seedlings were dipped in sterile distilled water for control. Three replications of each treatment were kept in a glasshouse at $28\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The seedlings were watered based on moisture requirements, and the

disease incidence was evaluated by frequently monitoring the seedlings for the manifestation of symptoms, virulence, and pathogenicity. Three replications were maintained for each isolate. The wilt incidence was determined as percent disease index (PDI) using the scale described earlier (Shanmugam and Kanoujia, 2011) as 0 = no symptoms; 1 = $\leq 25\%$ of the leaves with symptoms; 2 = 26–50% of the leaves with symptoms; 3 = 51–75% of the leaves with symptoms; and 4 = 76–100% of the leaves with symptoms. The PDI was calculated as follows: Disease index = $\sum (\text{rating} \times \text{the number of plants rated}) / \text{Total number of plants} \times \text{highest rating}] \times 100$. Disease severity was estimated as an average score, and each isolate's virulence was classified as low virulent (+), moderate virulent (++), or high virulent (+++) based on the disease severity. After surface sterilizing with 1% sodium hypochlorite, the pathogenic fungi were reisolated from the infected tissues exhibiting vascular browning by plating them on PDA. They were compared to the original culture in order to confirm Koch's hypotheses. The isolate with the highest wilt incidence was determined to be virulent.

Results and Discussion

The culture characters of 10 *Fusarium* isolates were studied. The colony growth, colour, sporulation, population of macro and micro conidia were recorded. It was observed that there were small variations in the cultural characters of these isolates. Details of information about the cultural characters were recorded (Table 1).

The pathogenicity test was done on 10 isolates using the soil inoculation technique to confirm the causative organism of wilt disease. Six-month-old guava seedlings were infected separately with the ten isolates that showed the highest percentage of wilting during the survey. The current analysis confirmed that all ten isolates of *F. oxysporum* caused guava wilt. Among them, two isolates of *F. oxysporum* f.sp. *psidii* were found to be extremely pathogenic with symptoms appearing within 60 days, but other *F. oxysporum* isolates showed delayed symptoms enduring more than 90 days and uninoculated plants showed no symptoms. Hussain et al. (2014) also revealed that after the onset of wilt symptoms, plants took 15 to 170 days to completely wilt and wilting was determined at 25.51% within the first 30 days and 78.57% cumulatively after 60 days.

Yellowing and browning of leaves was observed after 30 days of inoculation. Chlorosis with marginal scorching was observed after 45 days of inoculation. Shedding of leaves from the infected plants were observed after 60 days of inoculation. Complete drying and wilting of leaves was observed at the end of fourth month of inoculation whereas the uninoculated plants remains healthy and did not show any wilt symptoms with disease score 0. The splitted roots of the wilted plants showed brown colour discoloration of the vascular system. Similar results was determined by Gangaraj et al., (2022) and also proved that above mentioned disease symptoms and stated that *F. oxysporum* and *F. solani* were found to be highly associated with the wilt disease. These findings support Misra and Pandey's (2000b) observation of partial and complete wilting of inoculated plants, as well as brownish discoloration of the vascular bundles at the point of inoculation of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* and *F. solani*. Internal tissue and vascular bundle necrosis inhibits the transport of water and nutrients, resulting in wilting (Gupta et al. 2012). This pathogenic diversity observed in *Fusarium* is attributed to variations in pathogen strains, physical presence of pathogens, or toxic metabolites generated by different pathogens, which results in the formation of guava wilt disease (Misra and Gupta 2010).

The current study stated that soil inoculation technique also serves as a good technique for the reproduction of guava wilt in pot conditions as *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* produced 83 -85% (highly virulent) and *F. oxysporum* produced 60- 70% (Moderately virulent) of wilt symptoms (Table 2, Figure 1). Dasgupta and Rai (1947) also observed that *Fusarium* sp. causes symptoms after inoculation, but did not identify the species. Previously, Edward and Srivastava (1957) and Dwevedi et al. (1988) investigated pathogenicity in potted seedlings and confirmed *F. moniliforme* to be pathogenic in potted seedlings.

The varying period for symptom emergence may be attributable to the varied aggressiveness of various isolates. However, there was no association between the aggressiveness or virulence of isolates and their origin. Two *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* isolates were determined to be highly pathogenic out of ten *F. oxysporum* isolates. Edward (1960) examined 10 isolates of *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* and discovered that the pathogen appears to occur in a group of clonal forms that varied in virulence as well as physical and cultural characteristics. The varying duration required for *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* to produce symptoms may be attributable to the relative virulence of different isolates. However, no association was identified between isolate virulence and isolation location.

According to the findings of this study, *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* is the major pathogen of guava wilt. More *F. oxysporum* isolates were recovered in isolation than *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* isolates, showing its high frequency of occurrence in the field. In this context, the current work provides an approach to better management by identifying resistant donors or application of antifungal measures to combat the guava wilt disease.

Table 1: Progressive radial growth and sporulation of *Fusarium* spp. on PDA media under *in-vitro* conditions

S. No	Name of the isolate	Radial growth (cm)					No. of spores / ml	
		24hrs	48hrs	72hrs	96hrs	120hrs	Macroconidia	Microconidia
1.	GF1	3.65 ^a	4.83 ^a	5.48 ^b	7.91 ^a	9.00 ^a	3.8×10 ⁵	2.4×10 ⁵
2.	GF2	1.98 ^g	2.71 ⁱ	3.15 ^h	3.48 ^h	4.05 ^f	1.6×10 ⁵	1.4×10 ⁵
3.	GF3	3.43 ^b	4.61 ^b	5.12 ^c	5.43 ^d	6.15 ^c	3.4×10 ⁵	2.1×10 ⁵
4.	GF4	2.10 ^f	4.15 ^c	5.94 ^a	7.11 ^b	8.94 ^a	3.4×10 ⁵	2.3×10 ⁵
5.	GF5	2.87 ^c	3.54 ^{ef}	4.63 ^d	5.14 ^e	5.83 ^d	3.5×10 ⁵	2.1×10 ⁵
6.	GF6	2.89 ^c	3.94 ^d	4.19 ^f	4.43 ^g	4.86 ^e	2.9×10 ⁵	1.8×10 ⁵
7.	GF7	2.30 ^e	3.17 ^h	4.43 ^e	5.15 ^e	6.71 ^b	2.4×10 ⁵	1.7×10 ⁵
8.	GF8	2.31 ^e	3.26 ^{gh}	3.90 ^g	4.23 ^g	5.79 ^d	2.7×10 ⁵	1.5×10 ⁵
9.	GF9	2.15 ^f	3.40 ^{fg}	4.07 ^{fg}	4.68 ^f	5.01 ^e	3.2×10 ⁵	2.1×10 ⁵
10.	GF10	2.66 ^d	3.57 ^e	4.18 ^f	5.82 ^c	6.34 ^c	3.0×10 ⁵	1.6×10 ⁵
SEd		0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02		
CD(0.01)		0.04	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08		

Table 2: Virulence (Pathogenicity) of Fusarium isolates in Guava (Lucknow 49) under *in-vivo* condition:

S. No	Isolate	% disease incidence	Virulence
1.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>psidii</i> (TNAU 04)	85.76	+++
2.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 01)	42.64	+
3.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 02)	61.25	++
4.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>psidii</i> (TNAU 08)	84.25	+++
5.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 03)	58.92	++
6.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 05)	63.64	++
7.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 06)	68.15	++
8.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 07)	56.98	++
9.	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 09)	62.03	++
10	<i>F. oxysporum</i> (TNAU 10)	67.64	++

+++ - Highly virulent, ++ - Moderately virulent + - Less virulent

Figure 1: Virulence of Fusarium isolates in Guava (Lucknow 49) under *in-vivo* conditions

References

- Anonymous. 1953. Reports for the period 1946-1951. Directorate of Plant Protection, Quarantine and Storage New Delhi. 44p.
- Ashokkumar, N. and Poornima, K. Occurrence and distribution of root knot nematode, *Meloidogyne enterolobii* in guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) in Tamil Nadu. J. Pharmacogn. Phytochem. 2019, 8, 1922–1924.
- Ashokkumar, N, Poornima, K. Kalaiarasan, P. Embryogenesis, Penetration and Post penetration Development of *Meloidogyne enterolobii* in guava (*Psidium guajava* L.). Ann. Plant Prot. Sci. 2019, 27, 140–145.
- Chattopadhyay SB and Sengupta SK. 1955. Studies on wilt of guava L., in West Bengal. Indian J Hort 12 (2): 76-79.
- Das Gupta SN, Rai JN. 1947. Wilt disease of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.). Curr Sci. 16(8):256–258.
- Dwivedi SK, Misra RC and Dwivedi RS. 1988. Incidence of wilt disease of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) in Varanasi, India, Int J Trop Pl Dis 6 (2): 213-216.
- Edward JC and Srivastava RN. 1957. Studies on guava wilt. Allahabad Farmer 31 (6): 144-146.
- Edward JC. 1960. Variation in the guava wilt pathogen, *Fusarium oxysporum* f. *psidii*. Indian Phytopath 13 (1): 30-36.
- Gangaraj, R., Nagaraja, A., Gaba, S., Das, A., Prameeladevi, Debbarma, R., & Kamil, D. 2022. Occurrence, identification and pathogenicity of *Fusarium* species associated with guava wilt disease in India. Arch. Phytopathol. Pflanzenschutz. 55(2), 175-97.
- Gupta VK, Misra AK, Pandey BK. 2012. Histological changes in guava root during wilting induced by *Fusarium* spp. Arch Phytopathol Pflanzenschutz. 45(5):570–573.
- Hussain MZ, Rahman MA, Bashar MA. 2014. Incidence of guava (*Psidium guajava*) wilt caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* in Bangladesh. J Asiat Soc Bangladesh Sci. 40(1):97–105.

- Kala C, Gangopadhyay S, Goden SL. Ecofriendly management of wilt caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. ciceri in Chickpea. Legume Research 2016;39(1):129-134.
- Mathur RS and Jain SS. 1960. Selecting guavas for wilt resistance. Proc Natl Acad Sci, India, Sect B 30 (3) : 33-36.
- Misra AK and Pandey BK. 2000a. Pathogenicity and symptom production of wilt disease of guava by a new potent pathogen *Gliocladium roseum*. Proc Indian Phytopathological Society-Golden Jubilee, Int Conf, Integrated Disease Management for Sustainable Agriculture Vol. II Pub. Indian Phytopathological Society, New Delhi, India, pp749-750.
- Misra AK and Pandey BK. 2000b. Progressive natural wilting of guava plants during different months. Indian Phytopathology 53: 423-427.
- Misra AK and Shukla SK. 2002. Assessment of loss due to Guava wilt around Lucknow. Nat. Seminar on Production and Post-Harvest Technology of Guava. Dept. Hort. CSAUA&T, Kanpur, 9-10 January, 34-35p.
- Misra AK, Gupta VK. 2010. Relative pathogenicity of *Fusarium* wilt isolates to *Psidium guajava*. J Mycol Plant Pathol. 40(1):72.
- Pandey RR and Dwivedi RS. 1985. *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *psidii* as a pathogen causing wilt of guava in Varanasi district, India. Phytopathol Z 114 (3): 243 - 248.
- Prasad N, Mehta PR and Lal SB. 1952. *Fusarium* wilt of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) in Uttar Pradesh, India. Nature 169: 753.
- Shanmugam, V., & Kanoujia, N. (2011). Biological management of vascular wilt of tomato caused by *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lycospersici* by plant growth-promoting rhizobacterial mixture. Biological control, 57(2), 85-93.
- Sohi HS. 1985. Studies on wilt disease of guava. Annual Report, Indian Institute of Horticulture Research, Hassarghatta, Bangalore, 102 p.